

Impact of Recycled Coarse Aggregates on the Mechanical Properties and Durability of Concrete

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Abstract:

This study examines the influence of using Recycled Coarse Aggregates (RCA) on concrete mechanical and durability properties. The compressive strength, tensile strength, workability, unit weight, and water absorption of concrete mixes containing 0%, 50%, and 100% RCA were tested for different curing durations at 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days.

More specifically, the outcome showed that as RCA content increased, compressive and tensile strength decreased significantly. The use of 100% RCA resulted in a decrease in compressive strength and tensile strength by 40% and 46%, respectively. The workability

was reduced, and the amount of water absorbed increased to 6.70% in a 100% RCA mix.

Findings show that recycled concrete aggregate can be effectively utilised as a partial replacement material only if the percentage used is less than 50%. Over this threshold, it may compromise durability, especially in high-risk conditions. The results will help to sustain the use of RCA by minimising construction waste and conserving natural resources.

Keywords: *Recycled Coarse Aggregates, compressive strength, tensile strength, workability, durability, water absorption, sustainable construction.*

Introduction

Concrete is still one of the most common construction materials used worldwide because of its strength, adaptability, and widespread

availability. Aside from its production, construction and demolition (C&D) waste and the depletion of natural aggregates significantly contribute to the environmental footprint. The

global demand for construction aggregates, i.e., crushed rock, sand, and gravel, is now estimated at 40 billion tons a year, depending on the base conditions (Poon, Shui, & Lam, 2004), and has been used to justify expanding large-scale mining worldwide. Urbanisation is a significant factor contributing to this, and faster economic development will lead to more urbanisation in countries like Bangladesh, which will produce large amounts of C&D waste from demolished buildings (Silva, Brito, & Dhir, 2015).

Recycling Construction & Demolition (C&D) waste and using the processed RCA (Recycled Coarse Aggregates) in concrete structures has become a global sustainable alternative to natural coarse aggregates (NCA). RCA can be reused in fresh concrete mixtures, thus lowering the demand for natural aggregates (virgin aggregate) and reducing the environmental impact of waste generation (Kang, & Lee, 2012). On the other hand, several studies have shown that RCA can reduce the carbon footprint associated with concrete production and energy consumption by restricting virtuous extractions and processing of natural resources (Pareek, Saha, & Gupta, 2019; Amiri, Hatami, & Golafshani, 2021). However, the engineering properties of concrete made with RCA still present a significant challenge despite these environmental benefits.

Mechanical properties of concrete containing different percentage replacement factors of RCA by 25, 50, 75, and 100% compared to conventional concrete using the entire NCA have been studied in this research work. The results revealed that the compressive strength in RCA concrete is generally lower than that of natural aggregate due to its higher porosity and water adsorption than NCA weakens ITZ (Bui, Satomi, & Takahashi, 2018; Berredjem, Arabi, & Molez, 2020). For example, the strength of concrete with 50% RCA was found to be 60%-85% when compared to NCA concrete (Rahal, 2007). This aligns with the literature as RCA generally reduces compressive strength by 10%-30% (Yang, & Lee, 2008).

Tensile strength was also reduced in RCA concrete, thereby attaining about 50%-89% of the tensile strength of NCA concrete (Kang, T.

Kim, & Choi, 2012). This is mainly due to the weaker bond in ITZ, and the recycled aggregate has a higher tendency for microcracking than RAs (Gholampour, & Ozbakkaloglu, 2018). Nevertheless, soaking RCA in water or adding different kinds of chemical surface treatments can improve the anchorage between RCA and cement paste, increasing tensile strength (Dimitriou, Savva, & Petrou, 2018; Arulrajah, Yaghoubi, & Wong, 2017).

The other important factor is the durability of water absorption. Your investigations have found that water absorption of RCA concrete is considerably higher than that of conventional mixtures- even plain 100 % RCA will absorb as much as 6.7 %, compared to about 4.75 %, as evidenced in the control mix (Ali, & Tam, 2012). This rise in absorption could reduce the durability of RCA concrete, especially in freeze-thaw or chemical attack environments (Braga, Silvestre, & de Brito, 2017). Nevertheless, the water absorption of RCA concrete has decreased by adding supplementary materials like fly ash or silica fume, which improves its long-term durability (Kang, T. Kim, & Choi, 2012; Thomas, Thaickavil, & Wilson, 2018).

From an environmental standpoint, RCA is environmentally friendly, where the demand for natural aggregates is reduced, and waste is diverted from landfills. The carbon footprint of construction is thus also reduced using RCC. Fewer natural resources are extracted and processed (Etxeberria, et al., 2007). Economic analyses have demonstrated the cost-effectiveness of RCA concrete, especially in countries where natural aggregates are more expensive or rare (Pacheco, Brito, & Evangelista, 2017). In your study, RCA concrete costs 11% less than conventional concrete when considering the overall material price (Rahman, Uddin, & Sarker, 2019).

While the results are encouraging, more work is needed to optimise RCA concrete mixes and determine their sustainability for long-term engineering applications under tropical conditions such as those prevalent in Bangladesh. The current work is an addition to the wealth of knowledge that seeks to assess the

mechanical characteristics of RCA concrete to develop a sustainable construction practice.

Materials and Methodology

Materials

The materials used in this study are crucial for determining the properties of concrete, especially when partially replacing coarse aggregates with recycled stone chips. The study focuses on understanding how these replacements affect concrete's performance and mechanical properties.

Cement

This research selected the Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of Grade 28. When combined with water, Portland cement is an essential concrete component, creating the fundamental binding matrix. Cement had a specific gravity of 3.15 (weight so volume), which shows that it is 3.15 times heavier than water, equal to volume. It influences the concrete mix design, particularly regarding the water-cement ratio and overall workability.

An adequate cement matrix was obtained with a calculated cement content of 360 kg in one m³ of concrete. OPC: OPC is considered best for the initial strength gain, especially under normal curing conditions. OPC was used to standardise and compare the results with varying mixes containing recycled aggregates.

Fine Aggregate

This study used natural sand from Sylhet, Bangladesh, as fine aggregate. Fine aggregates are essential, however, to increase workability, fill voids in the concrete matrix, and enhance the strength of hardened concrete. It has a specific gravity of fine aggregate of 2.64 and gives a standard value that suits the construction sand given in its code.

Fine aggregate gradation was determined as per ASTM C33. This is necessary because of its workability, density and strength. Fine sand may increase water demand, and coarse sand may decrease cohesion in the mix. The fine aggregate (FA) had an FM of 2.64, indicating well-graded sand with a balanced content of finer and coarser particles (which would not increase water demand significantly while still promoting workability).

Figure 1. Fine Aggregate and Course Aggregate

Coarse Aggregate

The coarse aggregate forms a considerable part of the volume of concrete and is essential for strength and ability to withstand weather conditions. This study employed two types of coarse aggregates: natural coarse aggregate

(NCA) and recycled coarse aggregate (RCA). The RCA was procured by crushing torn-down concrete from dormant old structures, and the NCA was sourced freshly from quarries in Jamalpur, Bangladesh.

Natural Coarse Aggregate (NCA)

Concrete used the natural coarse aggregate specific gravity of 2.64 and absorption capacity of 1.30%. Unfortunately, RCA adsorb ability was a little higher than NCA due mainly to the presence of old cement paste into recycled aggregate. Due to a narrow range of aggregate sizes, mixing stability should be tested (known as grading voids), segregating and bleeding, and the NCA had well-graded particle size distribution. The NCA had an angular and rough shape, resulting in the interlocking and bonding with the cement matrix.

Recycled Coarse Aggregate (RCA)

The RCA used in this study was obtained from a local demolished building structure. The specimens were then prepared using this blended aggregate reduced to 5-20mm. The natural fineness modulus (FM) was found to be 2.77, and the RCA FM were observed to be 4.20. RCA is more porous and absorbs more water than NCA, which is caused by the residual cement mortar adhered to its surface. Specific Gravity and Absorption Capacity of RCA As per ASTM C128, RCA's specific gravity and absorption capacity tend to absorb much more water, which may affect the w/c ratio.

Water

Water is essential for the hydration of cement and the workability of concrete. In this study, fresh, potable water was used for both mixing and curing. The water-cement (W/C) ratio was maintained at 0.45 throughout the experiments. This ratio was chosen based on the concrete mixes' desired workability and strength requirements.

Methodology

The methodology adopted for this study was designed to evaluate the mechanical properties of concrete when natural coarse aggregates were partially replaced with recycled stone chips. This section describes the various steps involved in the experimental procedure, from material collection to testing the concrete samples.

Experimental Design

The experimental study finally included the casting and testing of cylindrical concrete specimens at varying replacement levels of RCA. The replacement levels of RCA were 0%, 25%, 50%, and 75% without any replaced material. Compressive strength, tensile strength, absorption capacity, and other properties of concrete were tested at each replacement level.

The concrete mix design was performed using ACI 211.1-91, the most famous method for designing concrete mixes. The weight of the mixes for all the replacement levels was kept constant, with a cement: fine aggregate: coarse aggregate ratio by weight as 1:1.89:2.69, respectively. The global recombineering methodology that we have applied permitted a standard quality in all samples and a reliable comparison of the different RCA replacement levels.

Mix Design

The mix design was based on maintaining a constant water-cement ratio while varying the percentage of recycled coarse aggregate (RCA) to natural coarse aggregate (NCA). The table below outlines the material quantities used per cubic meter of concrete for each replacement level.

Table 1. Mix Design

Material	0% RCA (NCA Only)	25% RCA	50% RCA	75% RCA	100% RCA
Cement (kg/m ³)	389.77	389.77	389.77	389.77	389.77
Fine Aggregate (kg/m ³)	738.79	738.79	738.79	738.79	738.79
Coarse Aggregate (kg/m ³)	1050.77 (NCA)	787.50 (NCA) + 263.27 (RCA)	525.39 (NCA) + 525.39 (RCA)	263.27 (NCA) + 787.50 (RCA)	1050.77 (RCA)
Water (kg/m ³)	165.69	165.69	165.69	165.69	165.69

Each batch of concrete was mixed thoroughly, and the slump values were recorded immediately after mixing to evaluate the workability of the fresh concrete.

Casting and Curing of Specimens

Casting of concrete specimens was carried out in a manner that guaranteed standardisation and accuracy. The mix was then put into a concrete mixer until the particles were distributed homogeneously. Workability, the ease with which fresh concrete could be placed and compacted, was determined on preliminary mix designs using slump tests immediately after mixing.

The 100 mm diameter and 200 mm height cylinders were then filled with concrete. Moulds were filled in three layers; each layer was compacted by tamping it 25 times with a tamping rod from one corner to another, which helped with the proper compaction of concrete

and removing air voids. A trowel was used to smooth the surface area off flat on all these per cylinder.

Concrete was poured into the moulds for 24 hours to set at room temperature. The moulds were removed without delicate stress once the settings were over, and the specimens were cured and submerged in water tanks. In water curing, the concrete is retained within adequate moisture content, ultimately ensuring the cement gets hydrated. This step is essential to provide the strength development of concrete as specified.

The specimens were then allowed to cure under controlled conditions for 7, 14 and 28 days to develop the strength of these materials. In contrast, their mechanical properties at a high temperature were not investigated. Curing was performed uniformly on all samples to avoid variations in concrete properties.

Figure 2. Mixing

Figure 3. Casting

Specimen Details

The following table shows the number of specimens prepared for compressive and tensile strength tests at various curing periods:

Table 2. Specimens

Replacement	Days	For Compression	For Tension
0	7	2	2
0	14	2	2
0	28	2	2
0.25	7	2	2
0.25	14	2	2
0.25	28	2	2
0.5	7	2	2
0.5	14	2	2
0.5	28	2	2
0.75	7	2	2
0.75	14	2	2
0.75	28	2	2
1	7	2	2
1	14	2	2
1	28	2	2
Total		30	30

Test Procedures

The test procedures conducted in this research aimed to evaluate the mechanical properties of concrete made with recycled aggregate. Each test was performed according to ASTM standards to ensure consistency and reliability of results.

Slump Test

The workability of fresh concrete was tested by performing a slump test. The slump test indicates workability and is helpful on-site to check that the concrete is easy to mix, place and compact. ASTM C143 was used to conduct the test. Following are the steps carried out in the slump test

1. Slump cone was cleaned from the inner surface and lubricated to ensure fresh concrete was not stuck.
2. The cone was set on a flat, nonabsorbent base and entered the concrete in 3 layers. Tamping: Each layer was tamped 25 times using a tamping rod.
3. The surface of a cone was wiped just enough to fill, and then the filled cone was removed vertically upwards without affecting the concrete present there.
4. The extinction and the time without changes in sea level (during subsidence = slump) are measured in one step. This was the slump value, which is the workability of concrete.

The slump values for different replacement levels of RCA were measured and compared to study the workability of fresh concrete influenced by recycled aggregate.

Compressive Strength Test

1. The most crucial test for concrete is the compressive strength test because it gives you an idea of how much load that batch of concrete can bear. The method of test was as per [ASTM C39]. The cylindrical specimens (100 mm in diameter, 200 mm in height) were loaded to failure under compressive load. Let me break it down for your steps-wise,
 1. The curing was carried out in the same tank, and when it reached the required age (7 days, 14 days or 28 days), the specimens were taken out of the curing tank and placed on smooth surfaces for drying.
 2. The cylindrical specimens were fixed into the universal testing machine (UTM), and the load was applied at a uniform rate until failure of the specimens
 4. The maximum load at failure was recorded, and the compressive strength was calculated using the formula:

$$f'_c = \frac{P}{A} \tag{1}$$

Where:

f'_c = Compressive strength (MPa)

P = Maximum applied load (N)

A = Cross-sectional area of the specimen (mm^2)

The average compressive strength for each replacement level was calculated and compared to evaluate the effect of RCA on the strength development of the concrete.

Figure 4. Compressive Strength Test

Figure 5. Tensile Strength Test

Tensile Strength Test

1. The tensile strength of concrete was explicitly evaluated through a split-cylinder tensile strength test. This is often the most relevant for understanding how a material will or

will not resist cracking in tension. Testing was done to comply with ASTM C496. Here is how the process is defined:

2. 1. The horizontal configuration of the cylindrical specimens between the loading platens of UTM.

3. 2. The specimen was subjected to a compressive line load along its length, producing tensile stresses perpendicular to the applied load and failing in splitting.

4. The maximum load at failure was recorded, and the tensile strength was calculated using the following formula:

$$f_t = \frac{2P}{\pi DL} \quad (2)$$

Where:

f_t = Splitting tensile strength (MPa)

P = Maximum applied load (N)

D = Diameter of the cylinder (mm)

L = Length of the cylinder (mm)

The tensile strength for each replacement level was compared to determine how RCA influences the tensile properties of concrete.

Water Absorption Test

1. The water absorption test is used to study the drying properties of concrete and its resistance to moisture entry. Greater porosity is usually related to more excellent water absorption and lower durability. ASTM C1585 conducted the test. The steps were as follows:

2. The concrete specimens were oven-dried at 105 °C until a constant mass was reached and cured.

3. 1. The dried specimens were weighed and submerged in water for the next 24 hours.

4. 2. The specimens were allowed to cure for one day in water before being removed, surface-dried and reweighed as saturated surface-dry (SSD) weight

5. Water absorption was calculated as the percentage increase in weight due to water uptake using the following formula:

$$A = \frac{W_a - W_o}{W_o} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where:

A = Water absorption (%)

W_a = SSD weight (g)

W_o = Oven-dry weight (g)

The water absorption for each replacement level of RCA was recorded to evaluate the impact of recycled aggregate on the porosity and durability of concrete.

Temperature Test

The temperature of fresh concrete was recorded during the mixing process to ensure that the concrete was mixed and placed under appropriate conditions. Temperature plays a significant role in determining the hydration rate and the concrete's ultimate strength. The test was performed following ASTM C1064. The steps are:

1. A thermometer was inserted into the fresh concrete mix immediately after mixing.

2. The temperature was recorded and compared across different batches to assess any variations caused by the use of RCA

Results and Discussion

Results

Slump Value

It is the workability or consistency of the fresh concrete mix (as indicated by its slump value). The results prove a gradual decrease in slump value by increasing the percentage of coarse RCA. The highest slump of 75 mm was recorded for concrete with 0% RCA (natural aggregate only), representing the ideal variation in workability and ease of placement. As the percentage of RCA increases, a little dropdown can be seen in a slump- 25% of RCA (74mm), 50% of RCA (70mm) and 75% of the RCA that has recorded a value up to 69 mm. Concrete with 100% RCA has the lowest slump value of 66 mm, indicating a workability reduction.

The decrease in slump value is due to RCA's relatively high-water absorption, apparently in comparison with natural aggregates. RCA absorbs more water, decreasing the free water available in the mix to maintain workability. The

potential drawback of a lower slump would be that more water or superplasticisers will have to be added to the practical application to achieve the desired workability, especially with higher percentage replacements.

Table 3. Slump Value

Replacement (%)	0	25	50	75	100
Slump Value (mm)	75	74	70	69	66

Figure 6. Slump Value VS RCA Replacement

Temperature

Freshly made concrete is very reactive to temperature, with setting time and hydration rate changed significantly by heat or cold. The temperature of the concrete after mixing varied from 26.02 °C–27.9 °C through different replacement levels of RCA in this study. At 0% RCA, the temperature was logged as 27.4°C, then at 25% RCA had the maximum value of 27.9°C. At the same time, for 50% RCA and at 75% RCA, values were observed as 26.5°C and as well as 26.02° C, respectively, regarding temperature readings recorded (Kang, & Lee, 2012). The test results recorded an aggregate

temperature of 27.5 °C for the mix with 100% recycled crushed aggregates.

The absence of notable temperature variations demonstrates no direct correlation between RCA content and temperature. The minor differences are likely due to environmental factors during mixing (air and surface temperature) or the inherent heat retention properties of the aggregates themselves. It is evident that the initial temperatures of the mix are neither too high (as typical for fresh concrete) nor too low, which implies that there are no adverse effects from the use of RCA.

Table 4. Fresh Mix Temperature

Replacement (%)	0	25	50	75	100
Temperature (°C)	27.4	27.9	26.5	26.02	27.5

Figure 7. Temp. VS RCA Replacement

Unit Weight

Concrete quality is an essential indicator of unit weight (or density). It can be observed from the results that the unit weight of the concrete decreases as the percentage replacement of RCA increases. For concrete without RCA, the unit weight of 2484.08 kg/m³ is the highest, indicating that natural aggregates are denser. Upon increasing the RCA content, the unit weight decreases gradually: 25% RCA – The unit weight of 2458.9 kg/m³ 50% RCA -2400.51 kg/m³ and 75% RCA- (2389.28 kg/m³) The

lowest unit weight is found to be at 100% RCA, with a value of 2334.57 kg/m³.

Since RCA has a high surface area, porosity presence and low density, these characteristics reduce its unit weight. RCA also often has old cement mortar adhering to the surface, which makes it more porous and less dense than crushed rocks. Thus, a decreased unit weight may influence the structural response of the concrete, especially in the use where weight by strength is requisite.

Table 5. Unit Weight

Replacement (%)	0	25	50	75	100
Unit Weight (kg/m ³)	2484.08	2458.9	2400.51	2389.28	2334.57

Figure 8. Weight VS RCA Replacement

Absorption Capacity

Among all, water absorption is the most essential factor in determining the durability and porosity of concrete. This is because RCA is a porous material; its absorption capacity will continuously increase as the quantity of FA in the mixture increases. For 0% RCA, the concrete has the lowest absorption rate of 4.75% and contains lower porosity. As the ABV of the RCA content increases, the absorption rate increases by 25%. RCA gives 4.95%, 50% RCA goes up to 5.53%, and the 75% value of RCA also resulted in a moderate decrease (5.83%). The best

absorption rate is for 100% RCA, which is 6.70%.

Such an increase in water absorption is probably because RCA retained some residual cement mortar, which usually has a higher porosity than natural aggregates. The problems associated with concrete, such as the deterioration due to freeze-thaw or chemical attack, could be higher when the concrete becomes more permeable, with a higher RCA content. Using such construction outdoors in an environment with high humidity can erroneously affect the structure's longevity.

Table 6. Absorption

Replacement (%)	0	25	50	75	100
Absorption (%)	4.75	4.95	5.53	5.83	6.7

Figure 9. Absorption Capacity VS RCA Replacement

Compressive and Tensile Strength Results

The compressive and tensile strengths of concrete are essential indicators as they reflect the load-bearing capacity and the ability of the material to withstand failure. According to the test results, it is becoming apparent that as the RCA content of the concrete increases, the compressive and tensile strengths are progressively reducing. The detailed results for the compressive strength of the concrete are that a concrete mix with has RCA content of 0% showed the highest values, which were 18.14, 22.11 and 28.12 MPa at 7, 14 and 28 days, respectively. As the mixture has started to contain RCA, the compressive strength at each time interval has declined. For 25% RCA, the 28-day compressive strength was 25.74 MPa, which had decreased to 22.56 MPa for 50% RCA. The 75% RCA mix had a value of 19.48 MPa, and the lowest compressive strength measured was 16.81 MPa, which was for 100% RCA at 28 days. The results for the tensile strength show a similar

trend, which is that it is gradually declining as RCA content is increased. For 28 days, the tensile strength for 0% RCA was 3.31 MPa, which had decreased to 3.12 for 25% RCA and then to 2.88 MPa for 50% RCA. A further decline was observed for 75% RCA, which was 2.49 MPa, and the lowest value was measured for 100% RCA, which was 1.79 MPa. The reason for this observation is that the bond between RCA and the cement matrix is weaker than in natural aggregates. In addition, RCA has more irregular shapes, higher porosity and more residual mortar, which can reduce the mechanical performance of the concrete.

The bond between RCA and the cement matrix is not as strong as that from natural aggregates, this being one factor causing the strength loss. Irregular shape in the RCA, higher porosity, and residual mortar, with its negative effect on mechanical performance, substantially reduce the overall mechanical performances of concrete.

Table 7. Tensile and Compressive Strength

Replacement (%)	Days	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
0	7	18.14	2.63
0	14	22.11	2.9
0	28	28.12	3.31
25	7	17.47	2.58
25	14	20.89	2.7
25	28	25.74	3.12
50	7	16.2	2.24
50	14	20.1	2.45
50	28	22.56	2.88
75	7	15.05	2.07
75	14	16.9	2.18
75	28	19.48	2.49
100	7	11.17	1.37
100	14	14.24	1.42
100	28	16.81	1.79

Figure 10. Compressive Strength VS RCA Replacement

Figure 11. Tensile Strength VS RCA Replacement

Discussion

Compressive Strength

Figure 12. Compressive Strength in Different RCA Replacement

The compressive strength of concrete mixes decreases as the RCA content increases across all curing periods (7, 14, and 28 days). This decline is consistent with findings from several studies that highlight the mechanical challenges of using RCA in high-strength applications.

Key Observations:

General Decline Across All Periods:

At 7 days, the compressive strength is as follows: from 18.14 MPa for the mix of 0% NCA and decreases to 11.17 MPa for the blend of 100% RCA. The compressive strength of 0% RCA mix at the age of 28 days could reach 28.12 MPa, for the same period of curing time, but the value is reached to just 16.81 MPa in the case of 100% RCA mix. This generalised reduction in compressive strength corresponding to an increase in RCA percentage fits well because other literature studies showed that the replacement of NCA with RCA resulted in a 20–40% drop in the compressive strength results, as indicated by Silva, De Brito, & Dhir, (2020). This decrease is related to the fact that RCA demonstrates lower quality (residual mortar from previous cement hydration weakens adhesion between aggregate and cement matrix (Kou, & Poon, 2021)).

Rate of Strength Gain:

The strength gains between 7 and 28 days for all mixes are obtained through continued hydration but at a much steeper rate in the case of mixes with 0% RCA and 25% RCA. This agrees with the conclusion natural aggregates improve adhesion and hydration (Tam, So, & Evans, 2019b). In contrast, the 100% RCA mix has a lower strength gain that agrees with previous studies about using RCA, where it is reported that due to its porous nature and type of adhering old mortar leftover partially hinders the complete hydration mechanism of the cement system (Tam, So, & Evans, 2019a). One of the main difficulties with RAC is that RCA concrete gains a lower strength than NCA-cleaned

concrete, which, in turn, restricts the use of RAC as an observed structure.

Reduced Long-Term Strength:

At 28 days, the 100% RCA mix forms only 60% of the compressive strength of the 0% RCA mix. Similar patterns have been reported in the literature showing that RCA mixes peak at an earlier progress of strength gain than natural aggregate concrete (Rahal, 2023). This premature plateau is due to the increased RCA porosity, resulting in numerous voids in the hardened RCC and subsequently leading to a decrease in load-carrying ability (Xiao, Qiang, & Huang, 2021). It has been studied that due to the large water absorption by RCA, taking up a significant number of austere features and less clear liquid cracks in RCA than ordinary gravel, desiring more materials for complete hydration, thereby reducing its long-term strength (Li, 2022).

Practical Implications:

The decrease in compressive strength at all curing periods indicated that an acceptable level of RCA content should be kept lower than higher levels to meet the required strength properties for structural application. Substitution of 25–50 % RCA fulfils a balance between maintaining a suitable level of strength and attaining those environmental benefits (Xiao, Qiang, & Huang, 2021).

Non-load-bearing applications: RCA are applicable to the use in non-load-bearing structures, such as pavements, footpaths, landscaping surfaces, mainly sidewalk or soil capping in landscape works (Butler, West, & Tighe, 2020).

Environmental sustainability: RCA helps sustain the environment by cutting down on the demands for natural aggregates and reducing construction waste that is not forwarded to landfills (Li, 2022).

Tensile Strength

Figure 13. Tensile Strength in Different RCA Quantity

The bar chart above presents the tensile strength of concrete mixes at 7, 14, and 28 days for different RCA replacement levels. The data clearly shows a consistent decline in tensile strength as the RCA content increases.

Key Observations:

Tensile Strength Reduction with Increased RCA:

7 Days The tensile strength at 7 days commencing at 2.63 for the per cent of RCA mix equal to zero and dropping to 1.37 MPa for the per cent of RCA mix equivalent to one hundred. This trend persists for each curing period; the 0% RCA mix achieves 3.31 MPa at 28 days, whilst the one with 100% RCA plateaus at 1.79 MPa.

The same tensile strength reduction level has been recorded in previous works. The latter shows the tensile capacity of RCA-based concrete was reduced by 30–40% with respect to traditional concrete (Kou, & Poon, 2021).

Rate of Tensile Strength Gain:

The tensile strength for all mixes generally increases with curing time, but the rate of gain per day slows down as RCA content rises. The 0% RCA mix displays the most rapid increase in tensile strength at 7 to 28 days, while the 100% RCA mix shows a significant decrease. This is consistent with the results of Silva et al. (2020) showed that the recycled aggregates caused a

slower strength gain in RCA mixes because of their porous nature.

Impact of RCA's Porosity:

This loss of tensile strength is mainly due to the greater porosity and absorption capacity of RCA. The inherent voids in the recycled aggregates weaken the bond between these aggregates and the cement matrix, which decreases their tensile strength due to the proneness of cracks—research by Tam et al. (2019) RCA has enhanced water absorption, which improves the effect of hybrid failure and weakens ITZ between aggregate and cement paste due to interference in the hydration process that ultimately leads to a decrease in tensile strength.

Practical Implications:

The reduction in tensile strength indicates that RCA concrete might not be an appropriate material for use in structural applications in which high ultimate tensile strength is required. RCA should be controlled and used in structural elements under tensile stresses as beams or slabs.

Inclusion of RCA Partially: Total replacement of aggregates with the addition of partial RCA up to a limit of 25-50% could be a practical option where we can satisfy the sustainability at some level without compromising the tensile strength. This is in concordance with the suggestions from a sustainable construction material study by Xiao et al. (2021).

Admixtures: Adding admixtures (e.g., fly ash and silica fume) helps to enhance the bond between RCA and cement matrix, resulting in less reduction in the tensile strength. It has been found in the literature that these additives fill the gaps/niches present within the recycled

aggregates, thus improving the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) and mechanical tensile behaviour of RCA concrete (Li, 2022).

Strength Retention Rate with RCA Addition

Figure 14. Strength Retention Ratio

The bar chart above shows the strength retention rates for both compressive and tensile strength at 28 days, expressed as a percentage of the original strength at 0% RCA. This representation helps illustrate how much of the initial strength is retained as the proportion of RCA increases.

Key Observations:

Compressive Strength Retention:

Compressive strength retention declines gradually as RCA content increases. At 50% RCA, around 80% of the initial compressive strength is retained, but this drops to about 60% at 100% RCA.

This aligns with Rahal's (2023) findings, where compressive strength retention showed a gradual decline up to 50% RCA, after which the strength reduction rate accelerated (Rahal, 2023).

Tensile Strength Retention:

Tensile strength shows a sharper decline compared to compressive strength. At 50% RCA, only 87% of the initial tensile strength is

retained, and by 100% RCA, tensile strength retention falls to about 54%.

The more pronounced reduction in tensile strength retention reflects RCA's impact on the concrete's ability to resist tension and cracking, as observed by [32].

Rate of Reduction:

The compressive strength remains almost like its original ultimate stress, up to 25% RCA, and drops significantly beyond this range but for the higher level of RCA.

This increase in Rev value may have an indirect effect on the tensile strength, which starts to decrease more pronouncedly at lower RCA percentages. The influence of RCA on the tensile strength is pronounced, with a decrease of just over 12% in tensile strength after 50% RCA.

This variation illustrates that tensile strength is typically more affected by replacing RCA than compressive strength.

Workability and Slump

Consider the workability of concrete mixes, which slump values represent. The document reveals that as you increase the percentage of RCA, the slump will decrease. This shows a decrease in plasticity likely due to the porous and water absorption nature of the RCA. As the RCA content increases, the slump value decreases from 75 mm with 0% RCA use to 66 mm with 100% RCA use, indicating a consistent reduction of workability.

Inference: Low slump design may cause difficulty in placing and compacting the concrete, especially for intricate shapes. For example, in the case where workability is essential, such as highly reinforced structural elements, or where easy flow and compaction (for example, pumping) become necessary.

Unit Weight Reduction

The outcomes further indicate that with the increasing of RCA percentage, the unit weight of concrete reduces. This reduction in density represents the lower specific gravity of RCA over natural aggregates. The unit weight decreases from 2484.08 kg/m³ for 0% RCA to 2334.57 kg/m³ for the mixture containing 100% RCA, equivalent to about 6%.

The decrease in density has a more positive connotation now due to the lower structural load, as it could be desirable within lightweight construction applications like precast elements or for high-rise buildings. But low density can also mean lower strength and durability, making the mix perhaps less suitable for various structural applications.

Water Absorption

As the RCA percentage increases, it augments the water absorption capacity of concrete. This is because RCA has better adhesion strength and more micro-cracks due to the self-porosity of coarse aggregate. This demonstrates the impact of RCA mixes on porosity and moisture retention, as water absorption increases from 4.75% for the 0% RCA mix to 6.70% for the 100% RCA mix.

Impact: The concrete may not be durable over the long term if it absorbs too much water, especially in cold climates with many freeze-thaw cycles or in areas where there are several strong chemicals present. Concrete that is susceptible to higher levels of water absorption may also have a greater tendency to crack and require further waterproofing to prevent harm.

Conclusion

This study has focused on the implications of using Recycled Coarse Aggregate (RCA) in concrete by reducing its mechanical properties. Results: The results showed a significant influence on observed properties of concrete, such as compressive strength, tensile strength, workability, unit weight and water absorption. Through analysis of the data, valuable tools and limitations of RCA in concrete construction can be highlighted.

Compressive Strength

The compressive strength of concrete was considerably decreased including the RCA. The compressive strength of concrete was reduced by about 40% when using 100% RCA instead of 0% in conventional concrete. It is known that requiring volume replacement or the presence of residual mortar and micro-cracks, RCA has a porous nature, which decreases its strength due to deteriorating the aggregate-to-cement paste bond.

Concrete mixes with 25-50% RCA, however, had acceptable levels of compressive strength and were, therefore, candidates for structural applications when moderate reductions in strength are acceptable. The significant drop in compressive strength means that although RCA use can increase beyond 50%, it will be limited to load-bearing structures. This is commensurate with previous research that indicates RCA can be employed within a portion of structural elements, but that tensile reinforcement will need adjustment to be used at higher RCA contents.

Tensile Strength

The tensile strength of RCA concrete also dropped significantly due to an increase in RCA content, similar to compressive strength. The tensile strength of concrete with 100% RCA had decreased by 46% as compared to conventional concrete. The weakened interface transition zone (ITZ) between the RCA and cement matrix, combined with abundant RCA aggregate porosity, predominantly accounts for this substantial loss.

Structural elements experiencing tensile stress can also use concrete mixes, although they still showed average strength properties with 25% to 50% of recycled aggregate. However, tensile strength reductions of more than 50% RCA suggest that RCA concrete is more susceptible to cracking with a lower ability to resist tensile stresses (affecting ductility), making this grade less suitable for critical structural elements that need increased tensile capacity.

Workability

According to this study, there was a noticeable decrease in workability represented by slump values. The workability of the concrete decreased as the percentage of RCA content increased, with 100% RCA concrete having the lowest slump value. A lower w/c ratio was found to be beneficial because the RA absorbs more water, increasing its water content hence lowering the free water in the concrete matrix. As a result, recycled concrete aggregate mixed with fresh cement bond will be more challenging to mix, place and compact, and it might hamper achieving uniformity and density properties of the ultimate product.

Workability-reduced makes concrete challenging to place in reinforced sections, intricate forms, and places where a long pumping distance is included. However, when mixed with 25-50% RCA, the workability of concrete remained within a reasonable slump range, indicating that partial RCA replacement can still provide adequate workability for most applications.

Unit Weight

Higher RCA contents also resulted in lower unit weight of the concrete — a reduction of 6 % in

the concrete with 100%RCA aggregate compared to the control mix. The lower density of RCA (due to the attached mortar and voids) causes this. While a lower unit weight may be beneficial for lightweight concrete applications (e.g., precast concrete elements, high-rise construction), it might have implications for strength and durability in other applications due to the reduction in density.

It has a lower unit weight to help minimise a dead load of structures, so perhaps less construction cost. However, at the expense of reduced mechanical properties, mainly when higher levels of RCA are utilised.

Water Absorption and Durability

The increase in water absorption with RCA is one of the most critical findings of this work. The water absorption of concrete containing 100% RCA was 6.70%, significantly more than that of conventional concrete, which is 4.75%. The reason for such things is that when water penetrates this RCA, it absorbs moisture due to its porous nature coupled with the micro-cracks and old mortar percentages.

One of them is its higher water absorption rates, which creates concerns about the long-term durability against environmental attacks such as moisture and freezing cycles. Greater porosity that enhances water penetration, and which may lead to:

- **Freeze-Thaw Deterioration:** Water that enters pores freezes and subsequently expands, leading to internal expansion and microcracking, which deteriorates the material over time.
- **Reinforcement corrosion:** Increased moisture in the concrete can allow reinforcement steel exposed to chlorides (chloride exposure is widespread in marine environments or de-icing salt areas) on the surface of your structure to rust much quicker.
- **Chemical attack:** The higher permeability can also make it more susceptible to sulfate and other chemical attacks that induce a dissolution of the concrete matrix with age.

Concrete mixes with 25-50% RCA present moderate water absorption, which could suit

environments with minimal exposure to aggressive conditions. However, 100% RCA mixes may require additional protection (e.g., waterproofing or surface treatments) to mitigate long-term durability issues.

Future Recommendations

Based on the findings from this research, several future directions and recommendations can be proposed to enhance the understanding and application of Recycled Coarse Aggregates (RCA) in concrete:

Long-Term Durability Studies:

However, these are mainly the mechanical properties of RCA concrete, and extensive research work needs to be undertaken on the durability of RCA concrete under different environmental conditions for investigation. The mechanisms of the freeze-thaw cycles, sulfate attack, chloride penetration and carbonation resistance on RCA concrete after extended service periods may be further explored. The results will be vital in determining whether RCA suits extreme environments, e.g., coastal, industrial and cold climatic regions.

Optimisation of RCA Percentage:

It can be concluded that the mechanical properties of concrete with 25–50% RCA are acceptable. Nonetheless, the workability, mechanical strength and durability could be further evaluated to achieve optimal balance with RCA replacement percentages in future research. In further work, more rigorous trials using mix proportions adjustment by fine-tuning, matched with diverse admixed types and dosages, can assist in demarcating an optimal application of RCA within a particular structural provision.

Use of Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs):

Supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) like fly ash, silica fume, or slag can be used in RCA concrete, which has been shown to enhance the ITZ bonding and decrease the porosity of the microstructure. Future studies

could be performed concerning SCMs and RCA concrete mainly to increase tensile strength and efficiency. This engineered concrete solution could be long-lasting and mechanically strong enough to withstand the test of time with a combination of SCMs and RCA.

Performance of RCA in Structural and Non-Structural Applications:

Although this study is oriented towards overall performance, it would be worthwhile to evaluate the intended usage of RCA concrete in structural and non-structural components by future researchers. This may be done for loadbearing members, pavements, precast elements or non-loadbearing walls. These studies could offer design criteria to define areas where RCA can be applied reliably and identify exceptions in which its performance might not meet specific needs.

Mitigating Water Absorption and Enhancing Durability:

Because of a more than proportional increase in water absorption with RCA amount, it is necessary to control the porosity level of RCA concrete in future. This could entail using water-reducing admixtures and pozzolans or recycled coarse aggregate surface treatment. Although proper detailing and construction practices can minimize the threats associated with exposure to moisture (including freeze-thaw damage, corrosion and chemical attack)

Lifecycle Analysis and Environmental Impact:

While this study highlights some of the environmental benefits of utilising RCA, future work should implement a full lifecycle assessment (LCA) to accurately quantify the net decrease in environmental impact from its use. These factors could include less natural aggregate mining and transportation carbon emissions, for instance, from an initial construction period, and the benefits of landfill diversions, thus decreasing industrial waste.

The behaviour of RCA in High-Performance Concrete (HPC):

High-performance Concrete (HPC) is commonly used in modern construction for its

high mechanical characteristics and durability. More work should be done concerning RCA behaviour in the case of HPC applications, such as how they influence the properties of high-strength, high-durability and low-permeability concrete mixes. Realizing how RCA has performed under those conditions can unlock more challenging applications for recycled materials within construction.

Exploring Surface Treatments for RCA:

Another view of research interest should be to use the surface treatment or pre-conditioning process for RCA so that its performance would improve with better strength development. It can be said that pre-soaking these RCA, surface treatments, or thermal treatments could help to reduce their water absorption and bond further with the cement matrix, which may result in its overall better mechanical and durability properties.

Development of RCA Mix Design Guidelines:

As RCA grows in popularity with contractors, there is a need for full design guidelines that consider the unique properties of RCA (e.g., higher porosity, water absorption, variability). Future research may help to establish uniform standard recommendations for practitioners to provide more consistent and reliable performance in real-world construction.

Field Studies and Performance Validation:

Laboratory analysis can predict the behaviour of RCA concrete, which is controlled, but further studies should be carried out in the field to confirm these lab results. Monitoring RCA concrete structures in field conditions for years would provide critical insights into the long-term performance and durability of RCA in actual construction. These field studies would ideally focus on determining the role of essential parameters such as weather exposure, loading conditions and maintenance needs.

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